

Diethanolamine Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II)

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Complexes of diethanolamine of the composition $[ML_2]X_2$ or $[ML_2X_2]$ have been synthesised where $M = \text{Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)}$ and $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_2^-, \text{NCS}^-$ and ClO_4^- . These have been characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies.

ETHANOLAMINES i.e. monoethanolamine, diethanolamine and triethanolamine invoke lot of interest as ligands since they contain two types of donor atoms and the hydroxy group may coordinate as such or a may be deprotonated or behave as a bridging group. But strongly enough though a number of workers¹ have examined the behaviour of these ligands in solutions of varying pH, comparatively little attention has been paid to the solid complexes apart from a few stray reports²⁻⁴ of their formation and stoichiometry. Hughes and Rutt have studied⁵ the complexation behaviour of triethanolamine. But it has been found out from solution studies that these amines behave differently. So it was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation to the case of diethanolamine and this communication reports a number of complexes of diethanolamine with Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Ethanolic solution of metal salts were treated with diethanolamine in 1:2 proportion and shaken vigorously. Compounds separated out in certain cases whereas in other cases compounds were precipitated after refluxing the solution for half an hour and keeping overnight. These complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solutions of the complexes using Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility were measured by Gouy method at room temperature (25°). Infrared spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Beckman IR -20 and IR -12 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded in M/100 chloroform solution of complexes using Hilgerwatt uvispeck spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Diethanolamine can behave as a terdentate ligand, but in the present study it behaves as both terdentate and bidentate involving oxygen of the hydroxy group and the nitrogen of NH group. All the complexes have the composition $[ML_2]X_2$ excepting the cobalt chloride and thiocyanate complex which have the composition $[ML_2X_2]$ where L is diethanolamine and X is anion. Cobalt and nickel complexes are green in colour excepting cobalt chloride and thiocyanate complex. Zinc and cadmium complexes are white in colour. Molar conductance values of the complexes are high (Table 1) suggesting 1:2 electrolytic nature of the complexes and so the anions are uncoordinated, excepting the case of cobalt chloride and thiocyanate complexes where low conductance values show coordination of the anions. Magnetic moment values are in the range of 4.5-4.7, 2.9-3.2 B.M. in

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	Λ_M (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%metal		%nitrogen	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. $[\text{CoL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	8.5	4.9	17.05	17.34	3.85	4.11
2. $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	10.8	5.0	14.92	15.31	6.98	7.27
3. $[\text{CoL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	200	4.5	13.45	13.75	3.02	3.26
4. $[\text{CoL}_2](\text{NO}_2)_2$	210	4.5	15.38	15.81	7.21	7.51
5. $[\text{CoL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	230	4.7	12.28	12.59	2.68	2.99
6. $[\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	220	2.9	16.85	17.26	3.85	4.12
7. $[\text{NiL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	218	3.0	13.45	13.71	3.10	3.26
8. $[\text{NiL}_2](\text{NO}_2)_2$	225	2.9	14.63	14.95	6.55	7.13
9. $[\text{NiL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	240	3.1	12.25	12.55	2.64	2.99
10. $[\text{NiL}_2](\text{NOS})_2$	215	3.2	14.85	15.26	6.88	7.28
11. $[\text{ZnL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	220	—	18.65	18.83	7.85	8.01
12. $[\text{ZnL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	212	—	14.82	15.10	6.15	6.44
13. $[\text{ZnL}_2](\text{NO}_2)_2$	232	—	16.11	16.37	13.81	14.03
14. $[\text{ZnL}_2](\text{NCS})_2$	216	—	16.48	16.70	14.05	14.31
15. $[\text{ZnL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	235	—	13.35	13.78	5.65	5.90
16. $[\text{CdL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	215	—	28.54	28.98	6.84	7.12
17. $[\text{CdL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	225	—	23.43	23.64	5.45	5.80
18. $[\text{CdL}_2](\text{NCS})_2$	220	—	25.71	25.99	12.38	12.77
19. $[\text{CdL}_2](\text{NO}_2)_2$	235	—	25.88	26.13	12.22	12.54
20. $[\text{CdL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	242	—	21.25	21.56	5.15	5.37

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Compound No.	$\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	ν_{max} in k.k. (ϵ)
1.	3450 3150	3200	450	355	18.8(30), 8.2(7)
2.	3450 3150	3220	455	355	19.2(32), 8.5(7)
3.	3420 3150	3300	450	360	15.5(750)
4.	3410 3150	3300	455	365	15.8(850)
5.	3420 3170	3250	450	350	16.8(810)
6.	3400	3300	455	360	23.2(14), 16.0(6), 10.2(5)
7.	3410	3250	450	355	23.5(15), 16.2(7), 10.2(6)
8.	3420	330	455	360	23.8(16), 16.5(7), 10.6(6)
9.	3410	3300	455	365	24.0(15), 16.5(6), 10.6(6)
10.	3400	3230	450	365	23.5(16), 16.5(6), 10.4(6)
11.	3390 3150	3300	425	370	
12.	3390 3160	3250	430	375	
13.	3400 3150	3300	420	370	
14.	3390 3150	3250	430	375	
15.	3450 3150	3300	425	370	
16.	3450 3170	3200	430	380	
17.	3450 3160	3300	430	380	
18.	3450 3170	3250	430	380	
19.	3390 3150	3300	435	375	
20.	3420 3160	3280	425	380	

case of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes suggesting a spin free tetrahedral and octahedral configuration respectively. The pink cobalt complexes of the formula $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]$ have moments in the range of 4.9-5.0 B.M. indicating a spin free octahedral stereochemistry for them.

Infrared spectra show the nitrate and perchlorate complexes to have D_{3h} and T_d symmetry of the free ions. Absorption bands were observed in the 3000-3500 cm^{-1} region due to $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{NH}$ stretching vibrations. The hydroxy group absorption is less helpful than would be hoped owing to hydrogen bonding effects but Kirschner and Kiesling have distinguished⁶ free and coordinated hydroxy groups in complex tartarates. In cases of all cobalt, zinc and cadmium complexes two medium intensity bands appear in the hydroxy stretching region (Table 2) suggesting possibly the presence of free and coordinated hydroxy group and splitting of the

$-\text{NH}$ band suggests coordination through the nitrogen atom. But in case of nickel complexes only one band appears in the hydroxy group stretching region indicating that both the hydroxy groups and nitrogen of the $-\text{NH}$ group are coordinated. This has been further supported by observation⁷ of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N}) \sim 420-450$ and $350-380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region.

In the electronic spectra of cobalt(II) chloride and thiocyanate complexes two bands are observed 18.8-19.2 ($30 \cdot 10^2$) and 8.2-8.5 (7) k.k. regions attributable⁸ to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ transitions respectively. A spin free octahedral configuration is presumed for these complexes being supported by the magnetic moment data. Other cobalt complexes give rise to an intense band in the 15.5-16 (800) k.k. region assignable⁹ to ${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ transition. The other band was probably beyond the range of instrument used. Basing on the magnetic moment values, the position and intensity of the absorption band a tetrahedral structure is suggested for these complexes. All the nickel complexes exhibit three weak absorption bands 23.2-24.0, 16.0-16.5 and 10.2-10.6 k.k. regions assigned¹⁰ to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$ transitions respectively indicating. On symmetry and hence depending on the magnetic moment and spectral data on octahedral environment is possible around the nickel(II) ion.

Basing on analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data presumably tetrahedral stereochemistry is indicated for zinc and cadmium complexes.

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